

Integrated pest management smart technologies to precisely detect and control plant diseases. D.I. TSITSIGIANNIS. *Department of Crop Science, Laboratory of Plant Pathology, Agricultural University of Athens. E-mail: dimtsi@aua.gr*

The ever-increasing demands of international markets for safe food have led to the development of integrated plant protection strategies (IPMs) for a more efficient and sustainable agriculture and to more robust certification and control systems for agricultural products. Novel IPMs of particularly serious plant diseases and mycotoxin contamination of plant products are being developed using innovative smart agricultural systems. The purpose is to: (a) accelerate the prognosis of disease outbreaks through prediction models; (b) develop methods of artificial intelligent diagnosis using imaging techniques or mass spectrometry sensors; (c) evaluate novel biocontrol and chemical PPPs to control effectively the diseases; (d) develop innovative prototype sprayers actuating different nozzle types and adopting variable rate control based on canopy characteristics and disease development. Decision Support Systems (DSS) are also developed and validated based on computer-based knowledge systems that enable disease prediction and monitoring and determine the critical stages of the various plant protection spray interventions. The ultimate goal of smart technologies is to reduce the European agriculture reliance on agrochemicals resulting in lower residues and reduced impacts on human health.

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